

ON THE DESIGN OF BONDED PATCHES FOR ONE-SIDED REPAIR

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SUMMARY: Due to the load-path eccentricity caused by bonding one reinforcement to only one side of a thin plate, which causes a shift of the neutral plane away from that of the plate, one-sided bonded repair has a much lower repair efficiency than two-sided repair. It is shown that for a given patch design, the secondary bending not only results in a higher stress intensity factor as compared with two-sided repair, but also significantly increases the stresses in the bonded reinforcement and the adhesive layer. Three non-dimensional parameters have been identified which completely characterise the stress intensity factor, the stresses in the adhesive layer, and the stress distribution in the reinforcement directly above the crack. A parametric study shows that one efficient strategy to improve the repair effectiveness and to minimise the stresses in the adhesive layer and the patch is to increase the thickness of the reinforcement.

KEYWORDS: bonded repair, one-sided repair, stress intensity factor, design of patches, adhesive stresses.

INTRODUCTION

Bonded repairs can be classified into two categories: symmetrical or unsymmetric, which are frequently termed respectively as two-sided and one-sided. In the former case two identical reinforcements are bonded on the two faces of a cracked plate. This symmetric arrangement ensures that there is no out-of-plane bending over the repaired region, provided the cracked plate is subjected to extensional loads only. In practice, however, one-sided repair is often adopted in which a composite patch is applied to only one face of the panel to be repaired [1,2,3]. This is because most often, only one face of a component to be repaired is accessible and sometimes only one side of a structure is allowed to be patched, e.g., aircraft fuselage and wing sections. If in these cases the thin skin structures are well supported against out-of-plane deflection, for instance, by stiffeners attached to one side, it is acceptable to ignore the out-of-plane bending, thus permitting the problem to be analysed using the method established for symmetrical repairs [4,5,6]. However, if the structure is unsupported, out-of-plane bending may lead to lower repair efficiency as compared with two-sided repairs [7,8,9,10]. Furthermore, the out-of-plane bending near the crack region is expected to result in much higher shear and peel stresses in the adhesive layer. Consequently, rigorous analyses are called for not only to quantify the repair efficiency, but also for the purpose of assessing the strength and durability of the adhesive bonding.

FORMULATION AND NOTATION

The crack geometry to be considered is shown in Fig.1 with the appropriate coordinate system and notations. The plate is repaired by a patch bonded to one face of the cracked plate. The boundary conditions for the problem are that the surfaces of the crack are stress free and there is a prescribed stress system at infinity so that

$$\sigma_{yy} \rightarrow \sigma^\infty, \sigma_{xx} \rightarrow \lambda\sigma^\infty, \tau_{xy} \rightarrow \tau^\infty \quad \text{as } \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \rightarrow \infty \quad (0 < z < t_p) \quad (1a)$$

and

$$\sigma_{yy} = \tau_{xy} = 0 \quad (|x| < a, y = 0, 0 < z < t_p) \quad (1b)$$

where λ denotes a biaxiality ratio. By using the superposition principle it is easy to demonstrate that it is equivalent to solving the following mixed boundary value problem,

$$\text{plate: } \begin{cases} \sigma_{yy} = -\sigma_0(z), \tau_{xy} = -\tau_0(z) & (|x| < a, y = 0, 0 \leq z < t_p) \\ u_y = \frac{du_y}{dz} = 0 & (|x| \geq a, y = 0, 0 \leq z < t_p) \\ \sigma_{xx} \rightarrow 0, \sigma_{yy} \rightarrow 0, \tau_{xy} \rightarrow 0 & (\sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \rightarrow \infty, 0 \leq z < t_p) \end{cases} \quad (2a)$$

$$\text{patch: } u_y = \frac{du_y}{dz} = 0 \quad (|x| < \infty, y = 0, t_p + t_A \leq z < t_p + t_A + t_R) \quad (2a)$$

Without the bonded patch, it is obvious that $\sigma_0 = \sigma_{yy}^\infty, \tau_0 = \tau_{xy}^\infty$. After patching, however, the stresses along the prospective crack path are no longer equal to those prior to the application of reinforcement. Exact solutions of σ_0 and τ_0 are generally not available except for certain simple reinforcement shapes and loads [4].

Fig.1 Geometry and coordinate system of repaired crack:
(a) plan view, (b) cross-section along centre line ($x=0$).

In this article we will limit our attention to the tensile mode only, since the shear stress distribution is uncoupled with the bending deflection of the reinforced region, hence the shear mode can be solved by ignoring the bending deflection [11]. In the case of symmetric repair of elliptical shape, i.e. the cracked is fully supported against out-of-plane displacement or two patches are bonded on the two faces of the plate, Rose [4] presented an analytical solution of the stress distribution. The inclusion analogy adopted, however, is not readily applicable to the case of one-sided repairs, where the out-of-plane bending would considerably complicate the analysis. Nevertheless, approximate solutions can be derived assuming the stresses in the

reinforcement and the base plate are uniform everywhere within the reinforced portion, and there is no relative displacement between the plate and the reinforcement. In the special case that the plate and the reinforcement have the identical Poisson's ratio [11], the prospective normal stress in the base plate is given by the following equation [10],

Fig.2 Single strap joint representing one-sided repair: (a) configuration and coordinate, (b) schematic of the bending deformation of an internally loaded strap joint, (c) boundary conditions along the crack plane.

$$\sigma_{yy}(y=0, z) = \frac{\sigma^\infty}{1+S} + \frac{\sigma^\infty t_p (\bar{z} - t_p/2)(\bar{z} - z)}{I_t} \quad (0 < z < t_p) \quad (3)$$

where $S = E_R' t_R / E_P' t_P$ represents the stiffness ratio, I_t and \bar{z} denote the moment inertia and the position of the neutral plane of the composite plate consisting of the base plate and the reinforcement being rigidly bonded.

Since the stress distribution in the plate is linear in the thickness direction, it is convenient to define a membrane force N_0 and a bending moment M_0 ,

$$N_0 = \int_0^{t_p} \sigma_{yy}(y=0, z) dz \equiv \frac{\sigma^\infty t_p}{1+S} + \frac{\sigma^\infty t_p^2 (\bar{z} - t_p/2)^2}{I_t} \quad (4)$$

$$M_0 = \int_0^{t_p} \sigma_{yy}(y=0, z)(z - \bar{z}_p) dz \equiv \frac{\sigma^\infty t_p^4 (\bar{z} - t_p/2)}{12I_t} \quad (5)$$

hence the normal stress at coordinate z is given by

$$\sigma(z) = \frac{N_0}{t_p} - \frac{12M_0}{t_p^3} \left(z - \frac{t_p}{2}\right) \quad (0 < z < t_p) \quad (6)$$

According to the superposition principle, the strain energy release rate for the semi-infinite crack geometry shown in Fig.1(a) is equal to the work done by applying $-N_0$ and $-M_0$ to the crack faces, as depicted in Fig.2. Details are given below.

Asymptotic Limit of the Stress Intensity Factor

The total strain energy release rate for a semi-infinite crack may be expressed as

$$G_{\infty} t_p = N_0 u_0 + M_0 \theta_0 \quad (7)$$

where u_0 and θ_0 denote respectively the mid-plane displacement and rotation of the crack faces, as depicted in Fig.2. The root-mean-square of the stress intensity factor is $K_{\infty, rms} = \sqrt{E_p G_{\infty}}$ [10]. In order to determine these two quantities, it is necessary to analyse first the stresses or strains in the adhesive layer. The governing equations for the adhesive shear and peel strains, which are assumed to be constant through the adhesive thickness, are respectively,

$$\frac{d^3 \gamma^{(A)}}{dy^3} - \beta_s^2 \frac{d\gamma^{(A)}}{dy} = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{d^4 \varepsilon^{(A)}}{dy^4} + 4\kappa^4 \varepsilon^{(A)} = 0 \quad (9)$$

where

$$\beta^2 = \frac{G_A}{t_A} \left[\frac{1}{E'_p t_p} + \frac{1}{E'_R t_R} \right] \quad (10)$$

$$\kappa^4 = \frac{E_A}{4t_A} \left[\frac{1}{D_P} + \frac{1}{D_R} \right] \quad (11)$$

where G_A and t_A represent the shear modulus and the thickness of the adhesive layer, D_P and D_R refer to the bending stiffness of the plate and reinforcement, $D_{P,R} = E'_{P,R} t_{P,R}^3 / 12$, and $E'_A = 2\mu_A / (1 - \nu)$ is the Young's modulus of the adhesive under plane strain condition. The differential equation (8) has the following solution in the domain $y > 0$,

$$\gamma^{(A)} = \gamma_{\max}^{(A)} e^{-\beta_s y} \quad (12)$$

where $\gamma_{\max}^{(A)}$ represents the maximum shear strain at $y=0$. Similarly the relevant solution for the adhesive peel stress in the case of semi-infinite overlap in the domain $y > 0$ is,

$$\varepsilon^{(A)} = (A \cos \kappa y + B \sin \kappa y) e^{-\kappa y} \quad (13)$$

The three unknowns, $\gamma_{\max}^{(A)}$ and constants A and B need to be determined from the appropriate boundary conditions.

The boundary condition for the shear strain is,

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{d\gamma^{(A)}}{dy} \right|_{y=0} &= \frac{\varepsilon_R(z = t_p + t_A) - \varepsilon_P(z = t_p)}{t_A} \\ &= \frac{1}{t_A} \left[\frac{1}{E'_R t_R} + \frac{1}{E'_P t_P} + \frac{3(t_R + t_P)}{E'_R t_R^2} \right] N_0 + \frac{6}{t_A} \left[\frac{1}{E'_R t_R^2} - \frac{1}{E'_P t_P^2} \right] M_0 \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The relevant boundary conditions for the adhesive peel strain at $y=0$ are,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left. \frac{d^2 \varepsilon^{(A)}}{dy^2} \right|_{y=0} &= \frac{1}{t_A} \frac{d^2(w_R - w_P)}{dy^2} \\
 &= \frac{1}{t_A} \left(\frac{M_R(y=0)}{D_R} - \frac{M_P(y=0)}{D_P} \right) \\
 &= \frac{1}{t_A D_R} \frac{t_R + t_P}{2} N_0 + \frac{1}{t_A D_R} \left[1 + \frac{D_R}{D_P} \right] M_0
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left. \frac{d^3 \varepsilon^{(A)}}{dy^3} \right|_{y=0} &= \frac{1}{t_A} \frac{d^3(w_R - w_P)}{dy^3} = \frac{1}{t_A} \left(\frac{V_R + \tau_{\max}^{(A)} t_R / 2}{D_R} - \frac{V_P + \tau_{\max}^{(A)} t_P / 2}{D_P} \right) \\
 &= \frac{\mu_A}{2t_A} \left(\frac{t_R}{D_R} - \frac{t_P}{D_P} \right) \gamma_{\max}
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

where the conditions that the shear force V_P and V_R are both zero at $y=0$ have been used.

From condition (14) one obtains

$$\gamma_{\max}^{(A)} = -\frac{1}{2\beta t_A} \left[\frac{1}{E_R t_R} + \frac{1}{E_P t_P} + \frac{3(t_R + t_P)}{E_R t_R^2} \right] N_0 + \frac{6}{2\beta t_A} \left[\frac{1}{E_R t_R} - \frac{1}{E_P t_P} \right] M_0 \tag{17}$$

and referring to equations (15) and (16) we have,

$$-2\kappa^2 B = \frac{1}{t_A D_R} \frac{t_R + t_P}{2} N_0 + \frac{1}{t_A D_R} \left(1 + \frac{D_R}{D_P} \right) M_0 \tag{18}$$

$$2\kappa^3 (A + B) = \frac{G_A}{2t_A} \left(\frac{t_R}{D_R} - \frac{t_P}{D_P} \right) \gamma_{\max}^{(A)} \tag{19}$$

thus

$$\kappa(A - B) = \frac{G_A t_P}{4\kappa^2 t_A} \left(\frac{t_R}{D_R} - \frac{t_P}{D_P} \right) \gamma_{\max}^{(A)} + \frac{t_R + t_P}{2\kappa t_A D_R} N_0 + \frac{1}{\kappa t_A D_R} \left(1 + \frac{D_R}{D_P} \right) M_0 \tag{20}$$

Denote the rotation of the plate at $y=0$ as θ_0 , since $\partial w_R / \partial y|_{y=0} = 0$ because of symmetry, and $\varepsilon^{(A)} = (w_R - w_P) / t_A$, we have, by definition,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \theta_0 &= \left. \frac{\partial w_P}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} = \left. \frac{\partial(w_P - w_R)}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} = -t_A \left. \frac{\partial \varepsilon^{(A)}}{\partial y} \right|_{y=0} = \kappa t_A (A - B) \\
 &= \left\{ \frac{t_P + t_R}{2\kappa D_R} - \frac{G_A}{8\kappa^2 \beta t_A} \left[\frac{t_R}{D_R} - \frac{t_P}{D_P} \right] \left[\frac{1}{E_R t_R} + \frac{1}{E_P t_P} + \frac{t_R(t_R + t_P)}{4D_R} \right] \right\} N_0 \\
 &\quad + \left\{ \frac{1}{\kappa D_R} \left(1 + \frac{D_R}{D_P} \right) - \frac{G_A}{16\kappa^2 \beta t_A} \left[\frac{t_R}{D_R} - \frac{t_P}{D_P} \right]^2 \right\} M_0
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

The opening displacement at the mid-surface of the plate is,

$$\begin{aligned}
u_0 &= -\gamma_{\max}^{(A)} t_A + \theta_0 t_P / 2 \\
&= \left\{ \frac{t_P(t_R + t_P)}{4\kappa D_R} + \left[\frac{1}{E'_R t_R} + \frac{1}{E'_P t_P} + \frac{t_R(t_R + t_P)}{4D_R} \right] \left[\frac{1}{2\beta} - \frac{G_A t_P}{16\kappa^2 \beta t_A} \left(\frac{t_R}{D_R} - \frac{t_P}{D_P} \right) \right] \right\} N_0 \\
&\quad + \left\{ \frac{t_P}{2\kappa D_R} \left(1 + \frac{D_R}{D_P} \right) + \left[\frac{t_R}{2D_R} - \frac{t_P}{2D_P} \right] \left[\frac{1}{2\beta} - \frac{G_A t_P}{16\kappa^2 \beta t_A} \left(\frac{t_R}{D_R} - \frac{t_P}{D_P} \right) \right] \right\} M_0
\end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

A comparison between the present results and the finite element analysis of the single strap joint representing a one-sided repair geometry [10] is shown in Fig.3, demonstrating a very good agreement.

It is now possible to express the crack opening displacement and crack face rotation in terms of the membrane force and the bending moment in a matrix formulation,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u_0 \\ \theta_0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} \\ C_{21} & C_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_0 \\ M_0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{11} &= \frac{t_P(t_R + t_P)}{4\kappa D_R} + \left[\frac{1}{E'_R t_R} + \frac{1}{E'_P t_P} + \frac{t_R(t_R + t_P)}{4D_R} \right] \left[\frac{1}{2\beta} - \frac{G_A t_P}{16\kappa^2 \beta t_A} \left(\frac{t_R}{D_R} - \frac{t_P}{D_P} \right) \right] \\
C_{12} &= \frac{t_P}{2\kappa D_R} \left(1 + \frac{D_R}{D_P} \right) + \left(\frac{t_R}{2D_R} - \frac{t_P}{2D_P} \right) \left[\frac{1}{2\beta} - \frac{G_A t_P}{16\kappa^2 \beta t_A} \left(\frac{t_R}{D_R} - \frac{t_P}{D_P} \right) \right] \\
C_{21} &= \frac{t_R + t_P}{2\kappa D_R} - \frac{G_A}{8\kappa^2 \beta t_A} \left(\frac{t_R}{D_R} - \frac{t_P}{D_P} \right) \left[\frac{1}{E'_R t_R} + \frac{1}{E'_P t_P} + \frac{t_R(t_P + t_R)}{4D_R} \right] \\
C_{22} &= \frac{1}{\kappa D_R} \left(1 + \frac{D_R}{D_P} \right) - \frac{G_A}{16\kappa^2 \beta t_A} \left(\frac{t_R}{D_R} - \frac{t_P}{D_P} \right)^2
\end{aligned}$$

It is evident that the cross terms, c_{12} and c_{21} , are non-zero, indicative of the coupling between in-plane and out-of-plane deformation. According to the Maxwell's reciprocal relation, the matrix C should be symmetric, i.e., $C_{12} = C_{21}$. However, due to the approximate nature of the plate theory, the resulting matrix is not exactly symmetric, although the deviation from symmetry is small.

The strain energy release rate is given by

$$G_{\infty} t_P = N_0 u_0 + M_0 \theta_0 \equiv c_{11} N_0^2 + (c_{12} + c_{21}) N_0 M_0 + c_{22} M_0^2 \quad (24)$$

It can be readily proven that the strain energy release rate given by equation (24) is identical to that derived earlier [10], which is plotted in Fig.4 together with finite element results (denoted by symbols). It is seen that the theoretical prediction of the upper bound of the stress intensity factor, $K_{\infty, rms} = \sqrt{E_P G_{\infty}}$, agrees well with the finite element results.

Without losing generality, the extensional and bending stress intensity factors may also be expressed in terms of the membrane force and the bending moment,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} K_m \\ K_b \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} N_0 \\ M_0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

The strain energy release rate can therefore also be expressed as [10],

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_p G_\infty &= K_m^2 + \frac{1}{3} K_b^2 \\
 &\equiv \left(B_{11}^2 + \frac{1}{3} B_{21}^2 \right) N_0^2 + \left(2B_{11}B_{12} + \frac{2}{3} B_{21}B_{22} \right) N_0 M_0 + \left(B_{12}^2 + \frac{1}{3} B_{22}^2 \right) M_0^2
 \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Since the strain energy release rate given by equations (24) and (26) should be identical for arbitrary N_0 and M_0 , we have,

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_{11}^2 + \frac{1}{3} B_{21}^2 &= \frac{E_p}{t_p} C_{11} \\
 2B_{11}B_{12} + \frac{2}{3} B_{21}B_{22} &= \frac{E_p}{t_p} (C_{12} + C_{21}) \\
 B_{12}^2 + \frac{1}{3} B_{22}^2 &= \frac{E_p}{t_p} C_{22}
 \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

It is apparent that matrix [B] is indeterminate unless it is symmetric, as there are only three equations for four unknowns. Since the off-diagonal components b_{12} and b_{21} have different units, they are bound to be difference, hence the matrix [B] cannot be symmetric.

Fig.3 Comparison between theory and finite element analysis of single strap joint.

Fig.4 Stress intensity factors

Alternatively we can define the following matrix representation, noting that $N_0 = t_p \sigma_m$ and $M_0 = t_p^2 \sigma_b / 6$,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} K_m \\ K_b \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} \\ d_{21} & d_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_m \\ \sigma_b \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} t_p b_{11} & \frac{1}{6} t_p^2 b_{12} \\ t_p b_{21} & \frac{1}{6} t_p^2 b_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_m \\ \sigma_b \end{Bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

A set of equations similar to equation (27) can be obtained in terms of d_{ij} . Again, unless matrix [d] is symmetric, it is indeterminate. However, for the repair geometry considered in [10], the calculated ratio K_{\min} / K_{\max} by assuming matrix [d] being symmetric is equal to 0.543, while the finite element analysis gave an average of 0.24. It is thus clear that the energy method alone is insufficient to fully determine matrix [b] or [d]; a more rigorous analysis using crack bridging method is called for, which is the subject of a separate article.

Design Considerations against Static and Fatigue Failures

A one-sided bonded repair consists of three layers: the cracked plate, the reinforcement, and the adhesive. While the key objective is to reduce the stress intensity factor for the cracked plate, both the patch and the adhesive have to be adequately designed to sustain service loading without premature failures, either under static or fatigue conditions. For a given cracked plate (characterised by three parameters: E_p , ν_p , t_p), the patch design involves essentially selecting a reinforcement (E_R , ν_R , t_R) and a structural adhesive (E_A , ν_A , t_A) to achieve the maximum reduction in the plate stress intensity factor and to ensure both the patch and the adhesive layer to sustain the design load. This implies that we need to find the optimum combination of six variables. This clearly requires a detailed parametric study to investigate the influences of each individual variable. To this end, it has been shown that the stress intensity factor of a patched crack is fully characterised by three non-dimensional parameters [10], which are

$$F = \frac{E_p' t_A}{\mu_A t_p} \quad S = \frac{E_R' t_R}{E_p' t_p} \quad T = \frac{t_R}{t_p} \quad (29)$$

The first parameter, F , denotes the flexibility of the adhesive layer as compared with the plate [10,12]. Parameter S refers to the stiffness ratio, which is conventionally chosen to be unity [1]. While it suffices to consider the first two parameters for two-sided repairs, the third parameter, T , is an important parameter unique to one-sided repair. As shown later, this parameter plays an important role in deciding the optimum design of patches for one-sided repair. For a given cracked plate, it has been shown that the upper bound of the stress intensity factor decreases with an increase in the thickness ratio, implying that by choosing thicker reinforcement, the stress intensity factor can be significantly reduced.

Apart from the repair efficiency, it is also important to ensure the stresses in the patch and the adhesive layer are also kept sufficiently low so that they do not impose any threat to the structural integrity of a repair system. It is easy to show that the above three parameters also fully characterise the maximum stresses in the patch and the adhesive layer.

For the reinforcement, assuming the stress distribution is linear through the thickness, the maximum stress is given by,

$$\frac{\sigma_{\max}}{\sigma^{\infty}} = \frac{4}{T} + \frac{3}{T^2} \quad (30)$$

It is clear that the maximum patch stress decreases with an increase in the thickness ratio T . It is also noted that the patch stress is much higher than in symmetric repairs or fully supported one-sided repairs, as in this case the maximum patch stress is equal to t_p / t_R .

The maximum shear and peel stresses in the adhesive are respectively,

$$\frac{\tau_{\max}^{(A)}}{\sigma^{\infty}} = -\frac{1}{[FS(1+S)]^{1/2}} \left[2 + \frac{3}{2T} \right] \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_{\max}^{(A)}}{\sigma^{\infty}} = \frac{6(1-ST)}{(1-\nu_A)FST} \left[\frac{3(1+ST^2)}{(1-\nu_A)FST^2} \right]^{3/4} \frac{\tau_{\max}^{(A)}}{\sigma^{\infty}} + \frac{6(1+T)}{FST^2(1-\nu_A)} \left[\frac{3(1+ST^2)}{(1-\nu_A)FST^2} \right]^{1/2} \quad (32)$$

which are shown in Fig.5. It is clear that with the constraint of $S=1$ the maximum adhesive shear and peel stresses tend to reach a minimum level of 0.4 as $T \rightarrow \infty$. This level, however,

implies that the repair can be applied only to cracked plates with a maximum design limit of around 75 MPa, as the strength of most structural adhesives is limited to around 30 MPa. In order to design a repair for primary aircraft structures, the adhesive stresses have to be reduced to at least 10% of the plate stress. This means that the balanced reinforcement requirement has to be dropped.

(b)
Fig.5 Variations of (a) the adhesive shear stress and (b) adhesive peel stress with the thickness ratio for balanced repair ($S=1.0$)

Let us assume that the patch material has a Young's modulus three times that of the plate, i.e. $E_R = 3E_P$, the respective adhesive shear and peel stresses are plotted in Fig.6. It is seen that by choosing $T = 3$, the above mentioned design requirement can be achieved, provided the adhesive system is designed to give a flexibility ratio of $F=10$.

(b)
Fig.6 Influences of thickness ratio on (a) the adhesive shear stress and (b) adhesive peel stress.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions can be drawn from the present analysis,

1. Out-of-plane bending in one-sided repair results in lower repair efficiency and higher stresses in the patch and the adhesive layer.
2. Thicker patches are found to be effective in reducing the stress intensity factor of a patched crack and the stresses in the adhesive layer and the reinforcement.
3. Energetic method alone is insufficient to partition the total strain energy release rate into a membrane and bending component, as the relevant matrices are found to be unsymmetrical.
4. Formulas have been derived for the upper bound of the stress intensity factor of repaired cracks, the maximum normal stress in the reinforcement, and the maximum shear and peel stresses in the adhesive.

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